

Appendix to

**“Who is behind the Model? Classifying
Modelers based on Pragmatic Model Features”**

Andrea Burattin¹, Pnina Soffer², Dirk Fahland³, Jan Mendling⁴, Hajo A. Reijers^{3,5}, Irene Vanderfeesten³, Matthias Weidlich⁶, and Barbara Weber^{1,7}

¹ Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

² University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

³ Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands

⁴ Vienna University of Economics and Business, Vienna, Austria

⁵ Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

⁶ Humboldt-University, Berlin, Germany

⁷ University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria

A Reference Models

Figure 1 reports graphical versions of the reference models of both modeling tasks presented in the paper.

The model presented in Figure 1a, used for the **pre-flight** task, describes the process performed by the crew of an airplane before taking off. The reference model has 12 activities orchestrated with 10 gateways. This model is fairly simple and comprises only sequences, parallel branches and optional activities. No nested blocks are reported in this case.

The model in Figure 1b was used for the **mortgage-1** task and it represents a mortgage application process. It contains 26 activities and 20 gateways. This process is more complex than **pre-flight** and comprises a long loop and several levels of nesting. Additionally, in this case, several end points are possible.

B Comparison of Different Classifiers

For the classification of the modeler we used 10 pragmatic model features. The features used are (for all details see the paper):

- F1 Alignment of fragments;
- F2 Percentage of activities in aligned fragments;
- F3 Percentage of activities in not aligned fragments.
- F4 Number of explicit gateways;
- F5 Number of implicit gateways;
- F6 Number of reused gateways;
- F7 Percentage of orthogonal segments;
- F8 Percentage of crossing edges;

F9 M-BP;
F10 Number of ending points.

In this appendix we compare the approach based of Neural Network with other different classifiers that can be used to achieve the same goal. We tested several simple classifiers and refrained to use more complex techniques (such as “deep learning”), since simple classifiers already achieve excellent performance.

All classifiers we used are referring to the Weka toolkit¹ and the full code of our prototype is available as open source². The classifiers we tested are:

1. Linear logistic regression models [1] with the default configuration of Weka;
2. Support Vector Machines trained with Sequential Minimal Optimization [2] (with Weka’s default parameters) and a polynomial kernel with degree 3;
3. Support Vector Machines trained with Sequential Minimal Optimization [2] (with Weka’s default parameters) and a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel with $\gamma = 5$;
4. C4.5 decision trees [3] as implemented in Weka’s J48 with default parameter configuration;
5. A multilayer perceptron feedforward artificial neural network trained with the backpropagation algorithm (with learning rate set to 0.3, momentum 0.2 and 500 training epochs), with one hidden layer containing 50 neurons [4]. A graphical representation of the neural network we used is reported in Figure 2;
6. A forest of random trees, also called Random Forest [5], with Weka’s default parameters.

The performance of these classifiers is reported in Figure 3 in terms of F1-score. Different dataset sizes have been considered and all tests are the results of 10-fold cross validation. Our results show that, except for logistic regression and SVM with a polynomial kernel, all other techniques perform very well (almost always above 0.8 for the `pre-flight` task and almost always above 0.9 for the `mortgage-1` task). The approach based on artificial neural network, which is described in the paper, is consistently performing very nicely, with just the Random Forests outperforming it, though by just a low margin.

The fact that all these classification techniques, which are very different from each other, are producing good results is an indication that the problem we are tackling (i.e., identifying the expertise level starting from pragmatic model features) is indeed solvable: results are not artificially caused by the specific classification technique used (e.g., due to representation bias). Instead, different machine learning methodologies are consistently producing high F1 scores, thus showing a spectrum of possible solutions.

Given the reported results, we can conclude that Random Forests achieve slightly better results compared to artificial neural networks. Therefore, to verify that all features are needed, we tested the performance of Random Forests on subsets of features. Results are reported in Figure 4 and the need for all features is confirmed: very high F1 values are achieved only when all features are available.

¹ See <http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/>.

² See <https://github.com/DTU-SPE/ExpertisePredictor4BPMN>.

Fig. 2: Graphical representation of the artificial neural network used.

(a) Performance of the classifiers on the pre-flight task.

(b) Performance of classifiers on the mortgage-1 task.

Fig. 3: F-scores of different classifiers on 10-fold cross validation tests, performed on different dataset sizes (models randomly selected), for the two tasks.

(a) Performance using F1, F2, F3.

(b) Performance using F4, F5, F6.

(c) Performance using F7 and F8.

(d) Performance using F9 and F10.

Fig. 4: F-scores on 10-fold cross validation tests on different dataset sizes, with different subsets of features. Each chart also reports the values obtained using all features. For this computation we used the Random Forest classifier.

References

1. Landwehr, N., Hall, M., Frank, E.: Logistic model trees. **95**(1-2) (2005) 161–205
2. Platt, J.: Fast training of support vector machines using sequential minimal optimization. In Schoelkopf, B., Burges, C., Smola, A., eds.: *Advances in Kernel Methods - Support Vector Learning*. MIT Press (1998)
3. Quinlan, R.: *C4.5: Programs for Machine Learning*. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, San Mateo, CA (1993)
4. Mitchell, T.M.: *Machine Learning*. McGraw-Hill (1997)
5. Breiman, L.: Random forests. *Machine Learning* **45**(1) (2001) 5–32